

A new spectrophotometric method for determination of trichloroacetic acid in air and environmental samples

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A new reagent system using *p*-aminoacetophenone for determination of trichloroacetic acid (TCA) is described. The method involves modification of Fujiwara reaction, i.e. discharging the colour obtained by adding pyridine and alkali, with acetic acid followed by the addition of *p*-aminoacetophenone. The purple-red coloured dye formed has an λ_{max} at 520 nm. The method has been satisfactorily applied for the determination of trichloroacetic acid in air and a variety of environmental and biological samples.

In view of the importance of trichloroacetic acid as a widely used herbicide, various instrumental methods have been reported¹. Spectrophotometric methods used for the determination of TCA are based on Fujiwara reaction^{2,3}, which involves the measurement of a red colour developed by the reaction between polyhalogenated compounds and pyridine in the presence of alkali. In the proposed method, the Fujiwara reaction has been modified for the determination of TCA. The method is based on the reaction of TCA with pyridine and alkali which on heating forms red coloured dye. The colour is discharged by addition of acetic acid and then *p*-aminoacetophenone (PAAP) is added which results in the formation of a purple-red coloured dye having an absorption maxima of 520 nm. The earlier methods reported used benzidine formic acid reagent which is carcinogenic while PAAP used here is non-toxic and has earlier been reported for the determination of isoproturan⁴ and atrazine⁵. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of TCA in various environmental and biological samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the dye formed showed maximum absorbance at 520 nm, where the reagent blank showed negligible absorbance. Beer's law was obeyed in the range 5.0–50 μg of TCA per 10 ml of the final solution (0.5–5.0 ppm). Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $2.61 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.006 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

The reproducibility of the method was checked by seven replicate analysis of a solution containing 10 μg of TCA per 10 ml of solution. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0069 and 4.66% respectively.

1 ml of pyridine and 2 ml of 5 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide were required for maximum colour intensity. Excess of sodium hydroxide made the solution cloudy. 2 ml of acetic acid was necessary for decolourisation of the

red colour. A minimum of 2 ml of PAAP was required for maximum colour intensity. It was observed that heating the reaction mixture for a minimum of 3 min in a water-bath at 70° gave optimal absorbance values. The purple-red coloured dye was found to be stable for ~10 min.

Effect of various co-pollutants and polyhalogenated compounds on the reaction was studied. The tolerance limit values (ppm) of different foreign species in a solution containing 10 $\mu\text{g}/10 \text{ ml}$ of TCA were found to be : DDT, Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} (1200); ethanol, methanol (750); Pb^{II} (650); nitrate, Sn^{II} , Ni^{II} (600); benzene, carbaryl, propoxur (550); ether (500); Hg^{II} (400); 2,4-D, 2,4,5-T (350); paraquat, BHC (250); malathion, parathion (200); phosphate (150). Chloroform gave positive interference.

Experimental

A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched silica cells was used. A Remi C-854/4 clinical centrifuge (1850 g) was used.

All the reagent used were of A.R. grade and double-distilled deionised water was used throughout.

A 1 mg cm^{-3} solution of pure distilled TCA was prepared in distilled water. Working standard was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. A 1% solution of *p*-aminoacetophenone (Ferak Berlin) in 25% alcohol. Aqueous solutions of NaOH (5 mol dm^{-3}) and HCl (10 mol dm^{-3}) were prepared.

TCA in air : A modified Wilson's procedure⁶ was used for determination of TCA in air. Air containing TCA vapours were drawn at the rate of 0.250 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for ~15 min through two midget impingers connected in a series containing 10 ml pyridine as absorbing solutions. Then aliquots of this solution were analysed by the proposed procedure. The recoveries were found to be 94–95% (Table 1).

TCA in soil : Soil samples from different areas where TCA was sprayed were collected. These sample (5 g) was dissolved in water, shaken thoroughly and filtered. The filtrate was subjected to centrifugation for ~10 min. To the

supernatant liquid 5% EDTA solution (1 ml) was added and analysed by the proposed method (Table 1).

Table 1. Determination of TCA in environmental samples

Sample	TCA added (μg)	Total TCA found (μg)		*Recovery %	
		Proposed method	Reported method	Proposed method	Reported method
Polluted : water ^a					
A	10	10.01	10.00	100.10	100.00
B	20	19.92	19.96	99.60	99.80
C	30	29.69	29.58	98.96	98.60
Soil ^b					
A	10	10.11	10.08	101.10	100.80
B	20	19.62	19.65	98.10	98.25
C	30	30.71	30.68	102.36	102.26
Air ^c					
A	10	9.50	9.35	95.00	93.50
B	20	18.80	18.77	94.00	93.85
C	30	28.26	28.30	94.20	94.33

*Mean of three replicate analysis.

^aAmount of water sample = 5 ml (run-off water from agricultural field where TCA was sprayed as herbicide)

^bAmount of soil sample = 5 g (soil sample from agricultural field where TCA was sprayed).

^cAmount of air = 3.75 dm³.

TCA in water : Water samples (collected from the run-off water from agricultural field where TCA was sprayed as a herbicide) were filtered and the filtered samples were analysed for TCA by the proposed method (Table 1).

TCA in biological samples : To check the recovery of TCA in the samples, known amount of TCA was added to TCA-free urine and blood serum samples. The solution was allowed to stand for ~2 h, filtered and the filtrate was analysed by the proposed method. The recovery was found to be ~96%.

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